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Mapping and monitoring regional inequalities in Brazil with the ST&I Geography Indicators of the ST&I Observatory

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Introduction

The Center for Management and Strategic Studies (CGEE) aims to promote scientific and technological development, and for that, among its objectives, it carries out prospective studies and research in the areas of education, science, technology and innovation. From the accumulation of these experiences and its constant search for innovative initiatives that dialogue with the needs of the National Science, Technology and Innovation System (SNCTI) in Brazil, the CGEE created the Science, Technology and Innovation Observatory (OCTI), which its main objective is to monitor scientific, technological and innovation production, following trends in Brazil and worldwide.

OCTI operates along two main lines of observation and analysis: a) the monitoring of scientific and technological production with the identification of trends and emerging themes in Brazil and in the world and b) the construction and monitoring of indicators related to key variables that condition the Brazilian ST&I area.

Within this scope, OCTI developed the Geography Indicators of ST&I in Brazil. It is a set of 18 indicators, which aims to assess the potential and bottlenecks related to ST&I in the Brazilian Regions and Federation Units.

This article presents the methodology and the results of the set of these indicators, aiming to identify the inequalities that exist between the Brazilian states and Regions, approaching different indicators in the dimensions of: inputs, processes, results and impacts. It also presents some of the visualizations and analyzes that can be made from these indicators, available on the OCTI Platform¹.

Context

A new pattern of development is increasingly consolidating on a world scale compared to what prevailed between the beginning and the end of the 80s of the 20th century (Fordism). This pattern is called Post-Fordism, Flexible Accumulation, V Industrial Revolution, Knowledge Capitalism or Cognitive Capitalism (SOJA, 1993; HARVEY, 2014; PÉREZ, 2010; SCOTT, 2012; ASHER, 2010).

Fordism was marked by the techno-economic paradigm of oil, automobiles and mass production, particularly consumer durables. In the case of Post-Fordism, this paradigm is characterized by the emergence of radical innovations, driven by Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) that have been changing the technological basis of the most diverse segments of economic activities.

Similar to what was observed in the emergence of Fordism, within the scope of this new standard, new technologies are implying transformations, not only in agricultural, industrial and service activities (4.0), but also in the Brazilian Regions and states of the Federation.

This historical process has left very striking and varied legacies in the trajectories of these regions. It can be said that, in addition to the South and Southeast regions, ‘three very different regional worlds’ were consolidated in Brazil: the North (Amazon), the Northeast and the Center-West. These ‘three worlds’ or Brazilian Regions are an amalgamation and superposition of social inequities, heterogeneous economic structures and poorly structured ST&I systems. These worlds present varied environmental, social, cultural, scientific and technological inequalities and diversities. The Brazilian economy, configured throughout the 20th century, ‘has reached a high degree of commercial and productive integration, endowing itself with a matrix network of relationships within and between economic segments, unevenly and selectively distributed throughout the country’ (BRANDÃO, 2019).

According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2020), ‘innovation is key for growth in all types of regions (...). What helps regions to innovate depends on the capacity of their regional innovation system (...). A few regions lead innovation in a progressively more complex environment. They expand the global knowledge frontier and thrive as innovation supports the creation of new jobs and productivity growth. Other regions are struggling to adapt their economies and are increasingly at risk of facing prolonged increases in unemployment due to automation or to job losses in traditional industries’.

As regional socioeconomic dynamics become increasingly conditioned by an intense process of diffusion of emerging technologies, linked to the post-Fordist techno-economic paradigm, ST&I initiatives gain relevance in the public policy agenda.

¹ Available at: <https://octi.cgee.org.br/>

According to the Ministry of Regional Development, the development of the Brazilian Regions ‘cannot be understood in a one-dimensional way. It is necessary to recognize regional inequalities at multiple scales of intervention, and guide policies and programs that promote territorial development through instruments suitable for multi-scale work, in order to facilitate federative cooperation and horizontal coordination of the federal government for its effective implementation’ (MDR, on-line)².

In this context, Decree No. 9,810/2019, which establishes the National Policy for Regional Development - PNDR, established, among others, the following sectoral axes or scales of intervention:

- a) productive development;
- b) science, technology and innovation; and
- c) education and professional qualification.

In order to reference the PNDR’s second axis, the Science, Technology and Innovation Observatory (CGEE) developed, in 2021, the CT&I Geography Indicators in Brazil.

An initiative that follows the proposals and paths adopted by other ST&I observatories, such as: The Network for Science and Technology Indicators – Ibero-American and Inter-American – (RICYT) Red de Indicadores de Ciencia y Tecnología - Iberoamericana e Interamericana - (RICYT), the Global Observatory of Science, Technology and Innovation Policy Instruments (GO-SPIN), and the Main Science and Technology Indicators of OECD.

These indicators aim to assess the potential and limitations of the different Brazilian Regions and federation units with regard to the conditions of key variables that condition the dynamics of their ST&I systems, given their relevance to regional and local development.

Methodology

The ST&I Geography Indicators were systematized according to a typology that, according to Gokhberg et al (2013), refers to the different types or natures that present vis a vis the dynamics of ST&I Systems: inputs, processes, results and impacts (Table 1).

² Available at:

<https://antigo.mdr.gov.br/desenvolvimento-regional-e-urbano/politica-nacional-de-desenvolvimento-regional>.

Table 1 - Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators: different natures

Input indicators	Process indicators	Output indicators	Impact indicators
Sources (financial, personnel, knowledge and technological) and public funding	Collaboration, partnership, HRST mobility and skills, technology transfer	Tacit knowledge (graduates, diplomas and certificates), codified knowledge and disembodied technologies (scientific publications, patents and their citations, licences, know-how etc.), embodied technologies and innovations (technological advances, new and advanced products and processes)	Direct impacts (sales, employment, market shares, final user adoption etc.), economic, social and other indirect impacts (CO ₂ savings, energy efficiency and other sustainable development indicators and responses to global challenges)

Each of these types of indicators has different dimensions, as detailed below, indicating their sources of information:

a) Input Indicators

- State government expenditures on R&D (MCTI);
- Financing (BNDES and FINEP);
- Expenditure by business entities in innovative activities (PINTEC);
- Human Resources in ST&I: training of Masters and Doctors (RAIS/ CGEE)

b) Process Indicators

- Cooperation networks (PINTEC and CNPq: Research Groups/Companies).

c) Results Indicators

- Bibliographic and technological production.

d) Impact Indicators

- Innovation in companies (PINTEC);
- Employment of Masters and Doctors;
- Growth of micro-establishments;
- Foreign Trade

Figure 1 presents the different types or natures of indicators, their respective dimensions and the list of indicators.

Figure 1: Indicators of ST&I Geography in Brazil according to nature and dimension

These indicators are calculated on the scales of the Brazilian Regions (North, Northeast, Midwest, South and Southeast) and Brazilian Federation Units.

In order to present and discuss these indicators, the Science, Technology and Innovation Observatory created an interactive digital platform, in the form of a radar chart, articulating indicators of different types or natures, dimensions and geographic scales. Each of these types, dimensions and their respective indicators are indicated according to different colors: in blue, Input; in black, Process; in brown, Results and, in orange, Impact (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2: Radar Chart representation of the CT&I Geography Indicators in Brazil.

As can be seen in Figures 2 and 3, the selection delimited in each geographic scale determines the situation represented by the indicator, allowing a joint visualization of the different types and dimensions. In Figure 2, for example, the mapping of the ST&I situation in Brazil can be used as one of the elements to analyze the ST&I system in the country.

In addition, it is possible to observe regional inequalities and success stories involving inputs, processes, results and impacts when exploring the tools of comparison between one or more geographic units. Some examples are presented in the following section.

Discussion and Results

The results of the indicators compose comparative analytical tables the Brazilian Regions and Federation Units, visualized in Radar Graph formats. Below, we explore some of the possibilities for analysis, focusing on how indicators can provide information on inequalities in the ST&I systems of the Regions and Brazilian Federation Units.

Figure 3 presents information for the Southeast and Northeast regions. The two regions present historical distances in the development of their ST&I systems that result in the inequalities that can be observed in their radar charts.

Figure 3: Indicators of CT&I Geography in Brazil, with the selection of the Southeast and Northeast Regions.

The Southeast Region (in purple) presents superior data in most of the indicators, numerically quantifying the comparative inequalities between the two regions. The highest expenditure values in indicators 1.1, 3.3, 8.1 and 8.2 (numbering as described in Figure 1) point to the greater development seen in the states of the Southeast Region. The higher level of financing indicators is also characteristic of the greater progress of the ST&I system in the region.

Some of the indicators with values similar to the Southeast Region, however, may indicate results of public policies and programs conducted in recent decades for the development of the Northeast Region, such as tax incentives for industry, the creation of technology parks and the increase in the availability of public universities. in the region. The highest values in indicators 9.1 and 9.2 (relating to the growth of micro-establishments in strategic areas such as the development and licensing of computer programs and information technology services) point to a gain in competitiveness of the ST&I systems in the Northeastern states. Analysis reinforced by the high result in the rate of product and/or process innovation of companies in the extractive and transformation industries (indicator 7.1) presented by the Region.

The differences in values between São Paulo (light green), Rio de Janeiro (dark green) and Amazonas (red), three states with different historical processes of development of their ST&I systems can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Indicators of CT&I Geography in Brazil, with the selection of São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro and Amazonas

São Paulo, for example, presents high values of indicators 1.1, 3.3 and 10.1 Results that indicate, in the state of São Paulo, the existence of a more structured ST&I system and with innovations and technical-scientific human resources in the industries aligned with an export with characteristics of high and medium-high technological intensity. The petrochemical chain in Rio de Janeiro and its acquisition of masters and doctors for the industrial and service sectors involved can be connected with the relatively higher values of indicators 8.1 and 8.2.

The effects of recent policies to stimulate the scientific-technological development of the state of Amazonas can be revealed by the indicators of its ST&I system. Significant values of indicators 3.1, 3.2, 7.1, 9.1 were recorded, linked to factors involving innovation in the industrial sector and growth of micro-establishments of computer programs.

One of the examples of these policies is the implementation of the Manaus Free Trade Zone, which is a business and industrial area created in the city of Manaus, capital of the State of Amazonas, heavily concentrated in segments of greater technological intensity, whose main objective is to attract companies and promote greater occupation and territorial integration with the northern region of the country.

Figure 5: Indicators of CT&I Geography in Brazil, with the selection of the Central-West and South Regions

In general terms, there is a greater historical presence of manufacturing industries in the South Region. While the Midwest Region is marked by innovation in sectors linked to agribusiness. This fact may explain the higher values in indicators 8.1 and 10.1, linked to the presence of masters and doctors in the manufacturing industry and to exports of high and medium-high technological intensity. There is also a comparatively greater tradition of science and technology institutions in the southern states, a characteristic indicated by relatively higher values of indicators 4.1 and 4.2, which concern the training of masters and doctors.

The Radar Graph also allows for comparisons between states and regions, as seen in Figure 6 below, which compares the state of Amazonas (red) with data for its Region (green).

Figure 6: Indicators of CT&I Geography in Brazil, with the selection of the Amazonas State and North Region

The data indicates the leadership of the state of Amazonas, the largest Brazilian state and with a strong socioeconomic importance, within the North Region. The results can also mean impacts from the implementation of the Manaus Free Trade Zone, as previously mentioned. There is, however, a gap in some indicators that point to the needs of specific development

policies: as in indicators 4.1 and 4.2, on the training of qualified human resources, and 8.1 and 8.2, which measure their insertion in the industry.

Conclusion

These are examples of analyzes that can be performed using information and graphs available on the OCTI Platform. The comparison and possible exercises from the visualizations presented, either by the Radar Graphic or by other graphic solutions present on the Indicators page in the OCTI web environment, can provide evidence for the elaboration of public and private initiatives aimed at mitigating the inequalities in ST&I present in the Regions and units of the Brazilian Federation.

This Platform will be systematically updated, enabling managers in the federal governments and in the Federation units to take the indicators as references to monitor policies and guide decision-making.

More than new data and information, it is an invitation for joint reflection on important themes and challenges for the management and promotion of ST&I in the country, with which, based on the development of monitoring methodologies and systematic analyses, OCTI seeks to contribute.

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